

Opracował
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Funkcja „Forming”

Forming				
	Name	Data type	Default value	Comment
1	▼ Input			
2	EMG_STOP_INPUT	Bool		
3	▼ Output			
4	<Add new>			
5	▼ InOut			
6	▶ Station	*SingleStation*		
7	ReadinessLightOut	Bool		
8	QuickUpMovementValve...	Bool		
9	QuickDownMovementVal...	Bool		
10	SteamVentilationOut	Bool		
11	PressOutputOut	Bool		
12	UnpressOutputOut	Bool		
13	▼ Temp			
14	OpeningDistanceTemp	Real		
15	station_number	Int		
16	▼ Constant			
17	<Add new>			
18	▼ Return			
19	Forming	Void		

IF #Station.EmergencyStopPressed = FALSE THEN

 IF #Station.FormingProcessOn = TRUE THEN

 REGION ReadingDataFromActiveRecipe

 #Station.SinglCyclData.Pi := #Station.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[#Station.iterator];

 #Station.SinglCyclData.Ui := #Station.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressingTimes[#Station.iterator];

 #Station.SinglCyclData.SlowPressing_i :=
 #Station.ActiveRecipeData.SlowPressing[#Station.iterator];

 #Station.SinglCyclData.SlowUnpressing_i :=
 #Station.ActiveRecipeData.SlowUnpressing[#Station.iterator];

 IF #Station.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressToHighSensor[#Station.iterator] <= 3 THEN

 #OpeningDistanceTemp :=
 #Station.OpeningDistances[#Station.ActiveRecipeData.UnpressToHighSensor[#Station.iterator]];

 ELSE

 #OpeningDistanceTemp := #Station.OpeningDistances[3];

```

        END_IF;

        IF #Station.iterator < 19 THEN
        IF #Station.ActiveRecipeData.PressingTimes[#Station.iterator + 1] = 0 THEN
            #Station.LastProcess := TRUE;
        ELSE
            #Station.LastProcess := FALSE;
        END_IF;
        ELSIF #Station.iterator = 19 THEN
            #Station.LastProcess := TRUE;
        END_IF;
        END_REGION

        REGION FormingProcess
        CASE #Station.ProcessStatus OF

        "InitialDownMovement": // Statement section case 1
            REGION InitialDownMovement
            IF (#Station.DistSensor.Dist_cm > #Station.ActiveRecipeData.Distances[5]) THEN

                "FullSpeedMovement"(QuickDownMovementValve =>
                    #QuickDownMovementValveOut,
                    QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);
            ELSE
                //TODO - przetestować poniższy kod z warunkiem
                IF #Station.PressurePar.ClampPressure <
                #Station.PressurePar.MinimumOperatingPressure THEN
                    #Station.ProcessStatus := "PressureTooLowError";
                    #PressOutputOut := FALSE;
                    #Station.FormingProcessOn := FALSE;
                ELSE
                    IF #Station.SinglCyclData.SlowPressing_i > 0 THEN

```

```

        "SlowSpeedDown"(QuickDownMovementValve =>
#QuickDownMovementValveOut,
        QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);
                END_IF;

                #PressOutputOut := TRUE;
                #SteamVentilationOut := TRUE;
                #Station.ProcessStatus := "PressingMove";
                END_IF;

        END_IF;
END_REGION

"PressingMove":
REGION PressingMove
#Station.SinglCyclData.UnpressingDone := FALSE;
IF #Station.SinglCyclData.SlowPressing_i > 0 THEN
"SlowSpeedDown"(QuickDownMovementValve => #QuickDownMovementValveOut,
        QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);
                ELSE
"FullSpeedMovement"(QuickDownMovementValve =>
#QuickDownMovementValveOut,
        QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);
                END_IF;

IF #Station.DistSensor.Dist_cm <= #Station.MinimalDistance THEN
        #Station.Speed.SD_x0 := #Station.DistSensor.Dist_cm;
#Station.Speed.Speed_down[#Station.iterator] := 1000*((#Station.Speed.SD_x1 -
#Station.Speed.SD_x0)) / (#Station.Speed.delta_t);
        #Station.ProcessStatus := "PressingHoldOn";

```

```
END_IF;  
END_REGION
```

```
"PressingHoldOn":
```

```
REGION PressingHoldOn
```

```
IF #Station.PressurePar.ClampForceValue >=  
#Station.PressurePar.ClampForceUpperLimit THEN
```

```
#PressOutputOut := FALSE;
```

```
END_IF;
```

```
IF #Station.SinglCyclData.Pi_Counter >= #Station.SinglCyclData.Pi THEN
```

```
#Station.Speed.SD_x0 := #Station.DistSensor.Dist_cm;
```

```
#Station.Speed.delta_t := 0;
```

```
#Station.ProcessStatus := "UnpressingMove";
```

```
#PressOutputOut := FALSE;
```

```
#Station.SinglCyclData.Ui_Counter := 0;
```

```
END_IF;
```

```
IF #Station.SinglCyclData.FullSpeedOnPressingEnd = TRUE THEN
```

```
"FullSpeedMovement"(QuickDownMovementValve =>  
#QuickDownMovementValveOut,
```

```
QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);
```

```
END_IF;
```

```
END_REGION
```

```
"UnpressingMove":
```

```
REGION UnpressingMove
```

```
IF ((#Station.DistSensor.Dist_cm - #Station.MinimalDistance) * 10) <  
#OpeningDistanceTemp THEN
```

```
#PressOutputOut := FALSE;
```

```
#UnpressOutputOut := TRUE;
```

```

ELSE
#Station.SinglCyclData.UnpressingDone := TRUE;
IF #Station.LastProcess = TRUE THEN
"FullSpeedMovement"(QuickDownMovementValve =>
#QuickDownMovementValveOut,
QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);
#Station.ProcessStatus := "EndingMovementUp";
ELSE
#UnpressOutputOut := FALSE;
#Station.Speed.SD_x1 := #Station.DistSensor.Dist_cm;
#Station.Speed.Speed_up[#Station.iterator] := 1000*((#Station.Speed.SD_x1 -
#Station.Speed.SD_x0)) / (#Station.Speed.delta_t);
#Station.ProcessStatus := "UnpressingHold";
END_IF;
END_IF;

IF #Station.SinglCyclData.SlowUnpressing_i > 0 THEN
"SlowSpeedUp"(QuickDownMovementValve => #QuickDownMovementValveOut,
QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);
ELSE
"FullSpeedMovement"(QuickDownMovementValve =>
#QuickDownMovementValveOut,
QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);
END_IF;
END_REGION

"UnpressingHold":
REGION UnpressingHold
IF #Station.SinglCyclData.Ui_Counter >= #Station.SinglCyclData.Ui THEN
#Station.SinglCyclData.Pi_Counter := 0;

```

```
        #Station.SinglCyclData.Speed_down :=  
        #Station.Speed.Speed_down[#Station.iterator];  
#Station.SinglCyclData.Speed_up := #Station.Speed.Speed_up[#Station.iterator];
```

```
        IF #Station.iterator < 19 THEN  
        IF #Station.SinglCyclData.UnpressingDone = TRUE THEN  
            #Station.iterator += 1;  
            #Station.Speed.delta_t := 0;  
            #Station.ProcessStatus := "PressingMove";  
            #PressOutputOut := TRUE;  
            END_IF;  
        ELSE  
            #Station.ProcessStatus := "EndingMovementUp";  
            END_IF;  
        END_IF;  
    END_REGION
```

```
    "EndingMovementUp":  
    REGION EndingMovement  
    IF #Station.SensorsRegister.ActuatorUpPosition = TRUE THEN  
        #Station.FormingProcessOn := FALSE;  
        #SteamVentilationOut := FALSE;  
        #Station.Reception.ProductReceived := FALSE;  
        #Station.ProdData.DailyProduction += 1;  
        #Station.ProdData.TotalProduction += 1;  
        #Station.ProcessStatus := "ReadyToReceiveProduct";  
    ELSE  
    "FullSpeedMovement"(QuickDownMovementValve =>  
        #QuickDownMovementValveOut,  
        QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);
```



```

#PressOutputOut := FALSE;

//TODO - po zainstalowaniu modułu odbioru, trzeba to usunąć
#Station.Reception.ProductReceived := TRUE;

IF #Station.Reception.ProductReceived = TRUE THEN
    #ReadinessLightOut := TRUE;
    ELSE
    #ReadinessLightOut := FALSE;
    END_IF;
END_IF;

ELSIF (#Station.SensorsRegister.DownMovementOverride = TRUE OR
#Station.SensorsRegister.UpMovementOverride = TRUE) THEN
    REGION MovementOverride
    IF NOT (#Station.Station_ID = 0) THEN
        "MovementOverride"(PressOutputOut := #PressOutputOut,
            UnpressOutputOut := #UnpressOutputOut,
            QuickDownMovementValveOut := #QuickDownMovementValveOut,
            QuickUpMovementValveOut := #QuickUpMovementValveOut,
            Station := #Station);
    END_IF; //TODO - jeśli chcemy utrzymać możliwość ręcznego sterowania ruchem, to
        należy skopiować funkcję powyżej
    //dla kolejnego stanowiska i przypisać właściwe jemu wyjścia z PLC
    END_REGION
    ELSE
IF #EMG_STOP_INPUT = TRUE AND #Station.EmergencyStopVirtualPressed = FALSE THEN
    REGION EMG_STOP_UNPRESSED_HANDLING
    IF #Station.ReturnToNominalPosition = TRUE AND
#Station.SensorsRegister.ActuatorUpPosition = FALSE THEN
    REGION ReturnToNominalPositionAfterEmergencyStop
    "FullSpeedMovement"(QuickDownMovementValve =>
        #QuickDownMovementValveOut,

```

```

QuickUpMovementValve => #QuickUpMovementValveOut);

    #UnpressOutputOut := TRUE;

    END_REGION

ELSIF #Station.ReturnToNominalPosition = TRUE AND
#Station.SensorsRegister.ActuatorUpPosition = TRUE THEN

    REGION ResetOutputsAfterReturning

    #QuickDownMovementValveOut := FALSE;

    #QuickUpMovementValveOut := FALSE;

    #UnpressOutputOut := FALSE;

    #Station.ReturnToNominalPosition := FALSE;

    END_REGION

    ELSE

    #QuickDownMovementValveOut := FALSE;

    #QuickUpMovementValveOut := FALSE;

    #UnpressOutputOut := FALSE;

    #PressOutputOut := FALSE;

    END_IF;

    END_REGION

    ELSE

    #QuickDownMovementValveOut := FALSE;

    #QuickUpMovementValveOut := FALSE;

    #UnpressOutputOut := FALSE;

    #PressOutputOut := FALSE;

    #Station.ReturnToNominalPosition := FALSE;

    END_IF;

    END_IF;

    END_REGION

    END_IF;

ELSE //PART TO HANDLE EMERGENCY STOP ACTION AND RETURNIG TO NOMINAL POSITION

    REGION EmergencyStopSituationHandling

```

```

        #PressOutputOut := FALSE;
        #UnpressOutputOut := FALSE;
        #Station.FormingProcessOn := FALSE;
#QuickDownMovementValveOut := FALSE;
        #QuickUpMovementValveOut := FALSE;
        #SteamVentilationOut := FALSE;
#Station.ReturnToNominalPosition := FALSE;
        END_REGION
        END_IF;

        IF #PressOutputOut = TRUE THEN
#Station.SensorsRegister.PressOutput := TRUE;
                ELSE
#Station.SensorsRegister.PressOutput := FALSE;
                END_IF;

        IF #UnpressOutputOut = TRUE THEN
#Station.SensorsRegister.UnpressOutput := TRUE;
                ELSE
#Station.SensorsRegister.UnpressOutput := FALSE;
                END_IF;

        IF #QuickDownMovementValveOut = TRUE THEN
#Station.SensorsRegister.QuickDownMovementValve := TRUE;
                ELSE
#Station.SensorsRegister.QuickDownMovementValve := FALSE;
                END_IF;

        IF #QuickUpMovementValveOut = TRUE THEN
#Station.SensorsRegister.QuickUpMovementValve := TRUE;
                ELSE
#Station.SensorsRegister.QuickUpMovementValve := FALSE;
                END_IF;

        IF #ReadinessLightOut = TRUE THEN

```

```
#Station.SensorsRegister.ReadinessLight := TRUE;
    ELSE
#Station.SensorsRegister.ReadinessLight := FALSE;
    END_IF;
    IF #SteamVentilationOut = TRUE THEN
#Station.SensorsRegister.SteamVentilation := TRUE;
    ELSE
#Station.SensorsRegister.SteamVentilation := FALSE;
    END_IF;
```

Koniec funkcji „Forming”

Funkcja „CopyStatesToStationDB”

CopyStatesToStationDB				
	Name	Data type	Default value	Comment
1	Input			
2	EMG_STOP_INPUT	Bool		
3	START_BTN#1	Bool		
4	START_BTN#2	Bool		
5	UP_SENSOR	Bool		
6	DOWN_SENSOR	Bool		
7	Output			
8	<Add new>			
9	InOut			
10	Station	*SingleStation*		
11	Temp			
12	<Add new>			
13	Constant			
14	<Add new>			
15	Return			
16	CopyStatesToStationDB	Void		

IF NOT (#Station.Station_ID = 0) THEN

IF ((#Station.EmergencyStopVirtualPressed = TRUE) OR (#EMG_STOP_INPUT = FALSE)) THEN

 #Station.EmergencyStopPressed := TRUE;

 #Station.ReturnToNominalPosition := FALSE;

 ELSE

 #Station.EmergencyStopPressed := FALSE;

 END_IF;

#Station.SensorsRegister.ActuatorDownPosition := #DOWN_SENSOR;

#Station.SensorsRegister.ActuatorUpPosition := #UP_SENSOR;

#Station.SensorsRegister.StartBtn1 := #"START_BTN#1";

#Station.SensorsRegister.StartBtn2 := #"START_BTN#2";

#Station.SensorsRegister.TemperatureDown :=

WORD_TO_INT(IN:="ThermocoupleK_DOWN_RIGHT")/10;

#Station.SensorsRegister.TemperatureUp := WORD_TO_INT(IN:="ThermocoupleK_UP_FRONT") /
10;

END_IF;

Koniec funkcji „CopyStatesToStationDB”

Funkcja „SendPID_ValuesToOutput”

SendPID_ValuesToOutput				
	Name	Data type	Default value	Comment
1	Input			
2	<Add new>			
3	Output			
4	<Add new>			
5	InOut			
6	<Add new>			
7	Temp			
8	station_number	Int		
9	Constant			
10	<Add new>			
11	Return			
12	SendPID_ValuesToOutput	Void		

```
FOR #station_number := 0 TO 3 DO
```

```
    CASE #station_number OF
```

```
        0:
```

```
            "PID_OutputSignalDown" :=
```

```
            "StationsDB".Stations[0].SensorsRegister.PID_OutputSignalDown;
```

```
            //TODO adding further conditions here is necessary to have proper heating
```

```
        END_CASE;
```

```
    CASE #station_number OF
```

```
        0:
```

```
            "PID_OutputSignalUp" := "StationsDB".Stations[0].SensorsRegister.PID_OutputSignalUp;
```

```
            //TODO adding further conditions here is necessary to have proper heating
```

```
        END_CASE;
```

```
    END_FOR;
```

Koniec funkcji „SendPID_ValuesToOutput”